

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GRAMMAR SKILLS AND SOME HINTS FOR ENHANCING STUDENT COOPERATIVE BEHAVIOR AND CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Qayumova Dildora

Uzbekistan Ferghana region, Besharik district

Secondary school -10

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6506704>

To develop one's speech means to acquire essential patterns of speech and grammar patterns in particular. Children must use these items automatically during speech-practice. The automatic use of grammar items in our speech (oral and written) supposes mastering some particular skills – the skills of using grammar items to express one's own thoughts, in other words to make up your sentences.

We must get so-called reproductive or active grammar skills.

A skill is treated as an automatic part of awareness. Automatization of the action is the main feature of a skill.

The nature of Automatization is characterized by that psychological structure of the action which adapts to the conditions of performing the action owing frequent experience. The action becomes more frequent, correct and accurate and the number of the operations is shortened while forming the skill the character of awareness of the action is changing, i.e. fullness of understanding is paid to the conditions and quality of performing to the control over it and regulation.

To form some skills is necessary to know that the process of the forming skills has some steps:

- Only some definite elements of the action are automatic.
- The Automatization occurs under more difficult conditions, when the child can't concentrate his attention on one element of the action.
- The whole structure of the action is improved and the automatization of its separate components is completed.

What features do the productive grammar skills have?

During our speech the reproductive grammar skills are formed together with lexis and intonation, they must express the speaker's intentions.

The actions in the structural setting of the lexis must be learnt.

The characteristic feature of the reproductive grammar skills is their flexibility. It doesn't depend on the level of Automatization, i.e. on perfection of skill here mean the original action: both the structure of sentence, and forms of

the words are reproduced by the speaker using different lexical material. If the child reproduces sentences and different words, which have been learnt by him as “a ready-made thing” he can say that there is no grammar skill. Learning the ready-made forms, word combinations and sentences occurs in the same way as learning lexis.

The grammar skill is based on the general conclusion. The grammar action can and must occur only in the definite lexical limits, on the definite lexical material. If the pupil can make up his sentence frequently, accurately and correctly from the grammatical point of view, he has got the grammar skill.

Teaching grammar at school using the theoretical knowledge brought some critical and led to confusion. All the grammatical rules were considered to be evil and there were some steps to avoid using them at school.

But when we learn grammatical items in models we use substitution and such a type of training gets rid of grammar or “neutralizes” it. By the way, teaching the skills to make up sentences by analogy is a step on the way of forming grammar skills. It isn't the lexical approach to grammar and it isn't neutralization of grammar, but using basic sentences in order to use exercises by analogy and to reduce number of grammar rules when forming the reproductive grammar skills.

To form the reproductive grammar skills we must follow such steps:

- Selection the model of sentence.
- Selection the form of the word and formation of wordforms.
- Selection the auxiliary words-preposition, articles, and etc. and their combination with principle words.

The main difficulty of the reproductive (active) grammar skills is to correspond the purposes of the statement, communicative approach (a question → an answer and so on), words, meanings, expressed by the grammatical patterns. In that case we use basic sentences, in order to answer the definite situation. The main factor of the forming of the reproductive grammar skill is that pupils need to learn the lexis of the language. They need to learn the meanings of the words and how they are used. We must be sure that our pupils are aware of the vocabulary they need at their level and they can use the words in order to form their own sentence. Each sentence contains a grammar structure. The mastering the grammar skill lets pupils save time and strength, energy, which can give opportunity to create. Learning a number of sentences containing the same grammatical structure and a lot of words containing the same grammatical form isn't rational. But the generalization of

the grammar item can relieve the work of the mental activity and let the teacher speed up the work and the children realize creative activities.

The process of creation is connected with the mastering of some speech stereotypes the grammatical substrat is hidden in basic sentences. Grammar is presented as itself. Such a presentation of grammar has its advantage: the grammar patterns of the basic sentences are connected with each other. But this approach gives pupils the opportunity to realize the grammar item better. The teaching must be based on grammar explanations and grammar rules. Grammar rules are to be understood as a special way of expressing communicative activity. The reproductive grammar skills suppose to master the grammar actions which are necessary for expressing thoughts in oral and written forms¹.

The automatic perception of the text supposes the reader to identify the grammar form according to the formal features of words, word combinations, sentences which must be combined with the definite meaning. One must learn the rules in order to identify different grammatical forms. Pupils should get to know their features, the ways of expressing them in the language. We teach children to read and audio by means of grammar. It reveals the relation between words in the sentence. Grammar is of great important when one teaches reading and auding.

The forming of the perceptive grammar and reproductive skills is quite different. The steps of the work is mastering the reproductive skills differ from the steps in mastering the perceptive skills. To master the reproductive grammar skills one should study the basic sentences or models. To master the perceptive grammar skills one should identify and analyze the grammar item. Though training is of great importance to realize the grammar item.

Classroom management and management of student conduct are skills that teachers acquire and develop over time. These skills almost never take a definite form until after a minimum of few years of teaching experience. To be sure effective teaching requires considerable skill in managing a number of tasks and situations that occur in the classroom each day. Skills such as effective classroom management are central to teaching and require "common sense", consistency, a sense of fairness, and courage. These skills also require that teachers understand in more than one way the psychological and developmental

¹ Lado Robert., "English pattern practices. Establishing the patterns as habits."; The univ. of Michigan, 1997., 190 p.

levels of their students. The skills associated with effective classroom management are only acquired with practice, feedback, and a willingness to learn from mistakes. Sadly this is often easier said than done. Certainly, a part of this problem is that there is no practical way for education students to “practice” their beginning skills outside of going into a classroom setting. The learning curve is steep, indeed.

The evidence is irrefutable, surveys of graduates of institutes and universities and other young new teachers of secondary schools, colleges or academic lyceums indicate that the first area of concern of new teachers is their feelings of inadequacy in managing classroom. Despite experiences, practicum, student teaching and other observations in classroom settings, this problem has persisted for decades. There is no single magic indication that will give skills in this area of professional responsibility.

As previously mentioned, personal experience and research indicate that many beginning teachers have difficulty effectively managing their classrooms. While there is no best solution for every problem or classroom setting, the following principles drawn from a number of sources, might help. Classroom teachers with many years of experience have contributed to an understanding of what works and what doesn't work in managing classrooms and the behavior of students. The following information represents some of the things that good classroom teachers do to maintain an atmosphere that enhances learning.

For an effective classroom management the classroom teachers should know what they want and what they don't want. And they should be able to show and tell the students what they want. When they get what they want they should acknowledge it. When they get something else they should act quickly and appropriately. In my opinion these are fundamental things that every teachers should take into consideration.

Good classroom arrangement is also effective in some way for classroom management but is not a guarantee of good behavior poor planning in this area can create conditions that lead to problems.

The teacher must be able to observe all students at all times and to monitor work and behavior. The teacher should also be able to see the door from his or her desk. Frequently used areas of the room and traffic lanes should be unobstructed and easily accessible. Students should be able to see the teacher and presentation area without undue turning or movement.

Commonly used classroom materials e.g books attendance, register book and student reference materials should be readily available.

Teachers should identify expectations for student behavior and communicate those expectations to students periodically.

Rules and procedures are the most common explicit expectations. A small number of general rules that emphasize appropriate behavior may be helpful. Rules should be posted in the classroom. Compliance with the rules should be monitored constantly but while arranging these classroom rules it is important to develop classroom rules that you are unwilling to enforce. One more thing must be mentioned that school wide regulations particularly, safety procedures should be explained carefully and posted in the classroom.

Because desirable student behavior may vary depending on the activity, explicit expectations for the following procedures are helpful in creating a smoothly functioning classroom.

-----Beginning and ending the period including attendance procedures and what students may or maynot do during these times.

___Use of materials and equipment.

___Seatwork

___How students are to answer questions for example, no student answer will be recognized unless he raises his hand and is called upon to answer by teacher.

In conclusion, we can say that, good discipline is much more likely to occur if the classroom setting and activities are structured on arranged to enhance cooperative behavior and classroom management.

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